

Dance Movement Therapy in the Treatment of Senior Citizens

Zhao Meng

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Abstract

In this study, the researcher looked on the level of effectiveness of dance movement therapy to the treatment of senior citizens. Given the lower physical activity and sedentary life of older adults, it was an area of research to look for the effects of dance movement, a kind of physical activity, to their functional fitness. The focus of this research was the effect of dance movement therapy to the functional fitness of senior citizens through a quantitative study. In order to gather the necessary data for this study, the researcher used experimental method to conduct a senior fitness test to measure the functional fitness of these older people. After gathering all the necessary data, the researcher tabulated, summarized and analyzed all the responses to come up with the results. Majority of the respondents were aged 60 to 65 years old with 55% while the lowest age bracket of the respondents were aged 71 to 75 years old. Gender was equally distributed with 25 respondents. Majority of the respondents were weighted above 66 kg with 40% and the least were weighted 50 to 60 kg. Senior citizens who were not engaged in dance movement have risky healthy conditions and Senior citizens who were engaged in dance movement have no risky healthy conditions. Dance movement therapy is having the physiologic capacity to perform normal everyday activities safely and independently without undue fatigue.

Introduction

Based from the Philippine Census in 2015, Filipinos age 64 years and above comprises 7.48% of the total population senior citizens to be exact. In line with the Philippine Constitution which states the importance of the family, including and giving emphasis to senior citizens, an act expanding the Senior Citizens Act of the Philippines was enacted in 2010. This strongly shows how we value our senior citizens, the living witnesses of our past and the people we always run and look up to. In a recent study, people over sixty (60) were found to be the least active and accumulate the most sedentary time of any other age group, regardless of whether they were working. This means that the functional fitness of older adults, specifically the senior citizens, was lower compared to their younger counterparts. Giving importance to our older adults should not end with just legislations that include discounts and other benefits, it should also be our duty to look after them and ensure that they were living well, physically and mentally, thus, also looking after their functional fitness (PSA, 2015).

Dance movement therapy was the ideal blend of physical exercise, social connection, and cerebral stimulation, and it had been shown to have both physical and mental advantages in studies. It was said to reduce blood pressure and cholesterol levels, enhance cardiovascular health, strengthen weight-bearing bones, assist in the prevention or slowing of bone loss associated with osteoporosis, lessen the dangers of obesity, and promote greater lung capacity in healthy individuals. When it comes to older folks, dance movement therapy may be a viable option to having them participate in a physical activity since they can gain the most from the benefits that dance movement therapy can provide to anybody at any age (Allen, 2017).

Elderly adults were encouraged to learn tango and dance movement therapy in order to reduce the likelihood of falling and harming themselves in the process. Tango and ballroom, which are slower, more organized dancing genres, give ankle and core strength for elderly adults, allowing them to maintain their balance better. Because of muscular degradation and a loss of balance that comes with age, as well as vision issues and medication side effects, older persons were shown to be at greater risk of falling. Senior people' functional fitness will be investigated in this study by the researcher, who will examine the impact of dance movement therapy on this population. Because older persons had lower

levels of physical activity and a more sedentary lifestyle, it was an area of study to investigate the benefits of dance movement therapy, which is a kind of physical exercise, on their functional fitness.

I. Research Objectives

Researches about dance movement therapy often focus on specific functions. In this study, the researcher will look into the effect of dance movement therapy of senior citizens who engage and not engage in dance movement therapy.

Specifically, it will seek to answer the following problems.

1. What is the profile of the respondents according to?
 - a. Age
 - b. Gender
 - c. Weight
2. What is the Senior Fitness Test Results of the respondents both engaged and not engaged in dance movement therapy in terms of?
 - a. Chair stand
 - b. Arm Curl
 - c. 6-Min Walk
 - d. 2-Min Step
 - e. (Chair Sit-&-Reach
 - f. Back Scratch
 - g. 8-Ft Up-&-Go
 - h. Dance steps

II. Theoretical Framework

According to the activity hypothesis of aging, there is a strong link between a person's level of activity and life satisfaction, which affects how positively an individual regards oneself or herself (self-concept) and also helps adaptability in later life. Despite the fact that these two ideas are not mutually incompatible, activity theory is typically compared with disengagement theory. Disengagement theory, proposed by Henry and Cummings in 1961, explains social disengagement as an adaptive response to aging in which older people renounce duties while preserving a sense of self-worth. This intentional cessation of enjoyment is said to allow for the orderly transfer of energy from older to younger generations, which benefits both the elderly and society. According to the activity hypothesis of aging, elder parents are happiest when they stay physically active and maintain social relationships. These activities, especially when important, help seniors restore lost life functions after retirement and, as a result, combat the societal forces that limit an elderly person's world. The idea presumes a positive relationship between exercise and life pleasure. Activity theory reflects the functionalist concept that the equilibrium that a person achieves in middle age should be maintained in later years. According to the notion, older persons who suffer job loss would replace past duties as well as new possibilities..

Despite this, years of gerontological study indicate that the activity design is much more exact than the disengagement model. Not only is exercise beneficial to the neighborhood, but it also engages more mature folks (both cognitively and physically) and helps them to get acquainted with others. This boosts emotions of pleasure and self-worth, both of which are necessary for lifespan and happiness.

III. Significance of the Study

Dance movement therapy was a topic that was not well researched about. In line with this this, this study was not only the academe but also fitness enthusiasts and individuals. In the academe, this study will give insights about the effect of dance movement therapy in dance movement therapy. This will also serve as an additional reference for future researches about this topic. Also, this study can help physical education (PE) teachers in improving their PE program. For the fitness enthusiasts, this study will help them reach more people by providing those evidences on how dance movement therapy improves one's physical activities. For the individuals, it helped them appreciate dance movement therapy more and it gave them an alternative to being fit.

IV. Related Literature

Dance movement therapy (DMT) is one of the most important professional organizations for psychotherapists. However, unlike verbal psychotherapy and unlike the most often suggested kinds of

psychotherapy for depression, such as cognitive behavioral therapy, DMT does not need the development of significant cognitive and language abilities on the part of the client or patient. Thus, it has the ability to overcome social and cultural boundaries. According to Karkou and Sanderson (2006), DMT, in conjunction with other arts treatments, is an appealing choice for clients because it helps them to deal with difficulties that are rooted at a non- and pre-verbal level of consciousness. So DMT may be an effective tool for working with difficulties that are difficult to verbalize or that have been buried in the unconscious due to the fact that they are unpleasant, scary, or just difficult to access and address using cognitive methods.

According to the findings of the study, weekly dancing practices were sufficient to alter brain development factors that enable brain plasticity in seniors. It has the potential to stimulate the parts of the brain that are connected with perception, emotions, executive function, memory, and motor abilities. Dance movement therapy (DMT) is considered to be a beneficial and acceptable solution for individuals who have difficulty communicating verbally, those who have cognitive impairments, and those who find it difficult to express and explore their feelings verbally. It also has a combination of physical and psychological health advantages.

DMT as a type of psychotherapy is a discussion of DMT as a form of psychotherapy that is more creative. Preparation, incubation, lighting, and assessment are the steps involved in this procedure. The key role of the movement metaphor within this process, as well as its connections to body memory, body language, and the mediation of the therapeutic relationship, are also identified by the author.

By Karkou and Sanderson (2006), for example, who reported on survey data that studied similarities and contrasts between DMT and the other arts treatments, DMT has also been investigated as one of the arts therapies. In particular, this research stated that DMT and other arts treatments have general therapeutic methods that are comparable to each other, including humanistic, psychodynamic, developmental, artistic/creative, active/directive, and eclectic/integrative therapeutic approaches. It is evident in these extremely demanding systematic reviews that it is difficult to capture the success of this area with varied client demographics when the included research are confined to designs of randomized controlled trials (RCTs).

Because the mind and the body are inextricably linked, every change in one of them has an immediate and negative influence on the other. In dance movement therapy, this characteristic of the body-mind link is often used to concentrate on a change in the quality of the client's movement without needing the client to be aware of those changes in their own movement. It is presumed that changes in movement capacity or changes in body processes may have important psychological repercussions, such as how decreased mobility might lead to a sense of powerlessness.

When they interact with one another, they have a tremendous deal of potential to either promote or hinder healthy aging. Aside from changes in physical activity, growing older increases one's susceptibility to chronic diseases and impairments, as well as one's overall quality of life. The combination of exercise and nutrition has been shown to be a useful approach for the elderly in a number of studies. In addition to increased physical activity and strength, improving or maintaining one's nutritional status in conjunction with exercise was associated with a number of other benefits, such as a lower incidence of sarcopenia, functional loss, and rehabilitation of musculoskeletal injuries, as well as a lower risk of and/or frequency of falls. Furthermore, improving gait and balance, as well as their overall quality of life, as well as lowering disease mortality and morbidity by 30% across the board. There is growing recognition that life satisfaction is a basic characteristic of well-being that acts as a protective factor for physical health and is becoming more significant in healthcare systems. Several studies have shown that dancing is the most enticing and stimulating activity for many people, particularly those from Asian backgrounds. According to Vahabi et al. (2012), the majority of people have taken part in some kind of dance at some time in their lives. A deep biological yearning for coordinated movement in response to rhythmic input was manifested via dance (Alpert, 2010), which brings back joyful memories, assists in the development of cultural connections with others, and provides an opportunity for socializing.

Dancing was similar to those of the rumba, although they were more rapid in nature. The hip movements were made by bending and straightening the knees. Fast movements are made by the feet and ankles, and the fast steps are maintained throughout the dance. These dances were considered to be physically taxing activities by the time they were performed. Beyond the health benefits, these dances may be performed anywhere (for example, at home or at a

dance school), at any time, with or without a partner, or as a group. They are also easy to learn. There have been no studies conducted to date that have looked at the psychological benefits of dancing among Filipino Americans, according to the researchers. It was unclear if first-generation Filipino Americans found dancing enjoyable or whether it encouraged them to engage in physical activity when they immigrated. Physical activity on a regular basis was deemed to be one of the most important lifestyle factors for maintaining great health into old age and increasing life expectancy in the study. The physical activities performed by older persons seem to have a good impact on both their cognitive and physical performance, according to survey results. Furthermore; physical activity in the elderly has been shown to be associated with increased survival.

V. Research Methodology

This research used an experimental strategy that resulted in multiple regression analysis, which entails manipulating one variable to evaluate if changes in one variable affect changes in another variable. To test a hypothesis, this approach employs controlled procedures, random assignment, and variable manipulation. Through a quantitative analysis, the aim of this research was the influence of dance movement therapy on the dance movement therapy of elderly persons. The researcher will perform a senior fitness test to assess the dancing movement therapy of these elderly folks in order to collect the essential data for this study. After collecting all of the relevant information, the researcher will tabulate, summarize, and evaluate all of the replies to provide the findings.

This study's participants were older adults who may have participated in dance movement therapy. The convenience sampling strategy was used to make data collection simpler for the researcher. Referrals and family connections were used to select the sample population. It was made up of 50 older people. There were 25 respondents who were involved in dance movement therapy and the other 25 who were not involved in dance movement treatment. Senior citizens with dementia, psychiatric problems, neurological disorders, mental deficit, and cerebrovascular accident with disability, blindness, deafness, and recent hospitalization were considered exclusion criteria for the two groups investigated.

As inclusion criteria, only older adults in excellent health who had attended at least 85 percent of the dance sessions were permitted to participate for participants who were engaged in dance movement therapy. In order to carry out this study, the researcher will compile a list of volunteers picked at random. These participants will be drawn from a group of senior citizen ballroom dancers spread throughout the country. In addition, the researcher will develop a waiver form for the subjects to sign. The waiver form should also contain a section that will get the participants' profiles, which will include basic information such as age, other dance or physical activity participated in, and frequency of dance movement therapy, among other things. To continue as a participant, the researcher must sign a release form that covers the study's privacy clause, the purpose of the study, and the tests they would be subjected to as a participant. To analyze the findings of this study, the collected data was analyzed using various statistical tools, such as obtaining the frequency percentage and weighted mean for the senior fitness test results, which were required in interpreting the results and will aid the researcher in formulating the conclusion and recommendations.

VI. Results and Analysis

I. Profile of the Respondents

Table 1.1
Demographic Profile of the Respondents

Age	F	%
60-65 years old	15	30
66-70 years old	16	32
71-75 years old	14	28
Above 76 years old	5	10
Total	50	100
Gender	F	%
Male	25	50

Female	25	50
Total	50	100.00
Weight	F	%
50 – 55 kg.	10	20
56 – 60 kg.	18	36
61 – 65 kg.	12	24
Above 66 kg.	10	20
Total	50	100.00

Majority of the respondents were aged 66 to 70 years old with 32% while the lowest age brackets of the respondents were aged above 76 years old. They were equally distributed with 25 respondents. This was often attributed to the relatively freer time of elderly women compared to men. The social worker in Manila also observed that there were OSCA activities which seemed to be geared toward female interests than the males, such as dance movement therapy and socials, thus more encouraging of females to join be more active in community events. It could be noted that majority of the respondents were weighted 56 kg to 60 kg with 18% and the least were weighted 50 to 55 kg.

Because the mind and the body are inextricably linked, every change in one of them has an immediate and negative influence on the other. In dance movement therapy, this characteristic of the body-mind link is often used to concentrate on a change in the quality of the client's movement without needing the client to be aware of those changes in their own movement. It is presumed that changes in movement capacity or changes in body processes may have important psychological repercussions, such as how decreased mobility might lead to a sense of powerlessness. While weight-related chronic illnesses cause high rates of mortality in persons of all ages, the chance of dying from weight-related disease rises with age, according to the American Journal of Clinical Nutrition. Furthermore, it has been shown that older persons who are obese have increased incidence of depression, particularly those aged 60-74. Obese persons' lungs shrink, making it easier to acquire respiratory difficulties. Because we naturally lose roughly 20% of our skin's dermal thickness as we age, older persons who are overweight or obese are more likely to get pressure sores. Being overweight or obese as a senior adult may induce or worsen significant illnesses cardiovascular disease and osteoporosis.

II. Senior Fitness Test Results (No Dance movement therapy Engagement)

Table 2.1. Chair Stand

Respondents	Chair stand (no. of stands)
1	5
2	4
3	7
4	6
5	6
6	6
7	5
8	11
9	7
10	7
11	5
12	4
13	7
14	6
15	6
16	6
17	5
18	11
19	7
20	7
21	5
22	4
23	7
24	6
25	6
Total	6.24

Table 2.1 represents the senior fitness test results with no dance movement therapy engagement. For chair stand, the weighted mean for these 10 respondents who were not engaged in dance movement therapy have 6.4 numbers of stands which falls into risk. As noted in Figure 3 and 4 for both men and women.

Normal Range of Scores - Men

	60-64	65-69	70-74	75-79	80-84	85-89	90-94
Chair stand (no. of stands)	14 - 19	12 - 18	12 - 17	11 - 17	10 - 15	8 - 14	7 - 12
Arm Curl (no. of reps)	16 - 22	15 - 21	14 - 21	13 - 19	13 - 19	11 - 17	10 - 14
6-Min Walk (no. of yds)	610 - 735	560 - 700	545 - 680	470 - 640	445 - 605	380 - 570	305 - 500
2-Min Step (no. of steps)	87 - 115	86 - 116	80 - 110	73 - 109	71 - 103	59 - 91	52 - 86
Chair Sit-&-Reach (inches +/-)	-2.5 - +4.0	-3.0 - +3.0	-3.5 - +2.5	-4.0 - +2.0	-5.5 - +1.5	-5.5 - +0.5	-6.5 - -0.5
Back Scratch (inches +/-)	-6.5 - +0.0	-7.5 - -1.0	-8.0 - -1.0	-9.0 - -2.0	-9.5 - -2.0	-10.0 - -3.0	-10.5 - -4.0
8-Ft Up-&-Go (seconds)	5.6 - 3.8	5.7 - 4.3	6.0 - 4.2	7.2 - 4.6	7.6 - 5.2	8.9 - 5.3	10.0 - 6.2

Figure 1. Normal Range of Scores in Men

Normal Range of Scores - Women

	60-64	65-69	70-74	75-79	80-84	85-89	90-94
Chair stand (no. of stands)	12 - 17	11 - 16	10 - 15	10 - 15	9 - 14	8 - 13	4 - 11
Arm Curl (no. of reps)	13 - 19	12 - 18	12 - 17	11 - 17	10 - 16	10 - 15	8 - 13
6-Min Walk (no. of yds)	545 - 660	500 - 635	480 - 615	430 - 585	385 - 540	340 - 510	275 - 440
2-Min Step (no. of steps)	75 - 107	73 - 107	68 - 101	68 - 100	60 - 91	55 - 85	44 - 72
Chair Sit-&-Reach (inches +/-)	-0.5 - +5.0	-0.5 - +4.5	-1.0 - +4.0	-1.5 - +3.5	-2.0 - +3.0	-2.5 - +2.5	-4.5 - +1.0
Back Scratch (inches +/-)	-3.0 - +1.5	-3.5 - +1.5	-4.0 - +1.0	-5.0 - +0.5	-5.5 - +0.0	-7.0 - -1.0	-8.0 - -1.0
8-Ft Up-&-Go (seconds)	6.0 - 4.4	6.4 - 4.8	7.1 - 4.9	7.4 - 5.2	8.7 - 5.7	9.6 - 6.2	11.5 - 7.3

Figure 2. Normal Range of Scores in Women

Table 2.2. Arm Curl

Respondents	Arm Curl
1	10

2	8
3	14
4	13
5	10
6	12
7	8
8	11
9	8
10	11
11	10
12	8
13	14
14	13
15	10
16	12
17	8
18	11
19	8
20	10
21	8
22	14
23	13
24	10
25	12
Weighted Mean	10.64

In arm curl, the weighted mean were 10.5 numbers of reps. It appears that both senior citizen men and women fell below average as measured in Figure 1 and 2.

Table 2.3
6 Min. Walk

Respondents	6-Min Walk (no.of yds)
1	25
2	20
3	40
4	38
5	30
6	40

7	23
8	30
9	20
10	28
11	25
12	20
13	40
14	38
15	30
16	40
17	23
18	30
19	20
20	28
21	25
22	20
23	40
24	38
25	30
Weighted Mean	29.64

For the 6 minutes' walk, both men and female senior citizen fell in risky condition with weighted mean of 29.4 yards only.

Table 2.4
2-Min Step

Respondents	2-Min Step
1	30
2	25
3	38
4	33
5	30
6	33
7	28
8	32
9	25
10	29

11	30
12	25
13	38
14	33
15	30
16	33
17	28
18	32
19	25
20	29
21	30
22	25
23	38
24	33
25	30
Weighted Mean	30.48

For 2-min step, both men and female senior citizen fell in risky condition with weighted mean of 30.3 steps only.

Table 2.5
Back Scratch

Respondents	Back Scratch
1	3 ½
2	3
3	3
4	2 ½
5	3
6	2 ½
7	3
8	3
9	3
10	3 ½
11	3 ½
12	3
13	3
14	2 ½
15	3
16	2 ½
17	3

18	3
19	3
20	3 ½
21	3 ½
22	3
23	3
24	2 ½
25	3
Weighted Mean	3

For Back Scratch, both men and female senior citizen fell in risky condition with weighted mean of 3 inches only.

Table 2.7
8-Ft Up-&-Go

Respondents	8-Ft Up-&-Go
1	10
2	11
3	13
4	11
5	15
6	11
7	7
8	117
9	8
10	9
11	10
12	11
13	13
14	11
15	15
16	11
17	7
18	117
19	8
20	10
21	11
22	13

23	11
24	15
25	11
Weighted Mean	19.44

And for 8-Ft Up-&-Go, both men and female senior citizen fell in risky condition with weighted mean of 10.6 seconds only.

Dancing increases strength and muscular function in older persons, as well as balance and flexibility, resulting in improved stability and fewer injuries, according to research. Dancing may also enhance your cardiovascular health, lowering your risk of acquiring heart disease. According to these findings, dancing, like any other kind of exercise, helps elders in a variety of ways. The gold standard suggestion for lowering the risk of dementia was regular physical, mental, and social stimulation. Dancing may be seen as a "triple-threat" choice for older folks who wish to maintain their brains since it incorporates all three. Seniors might get more of the heart- and brain-health advantages of exercise by selecting activities they like.

DMT was the perfect combination of physical exercise, social interaction, and brain stimulation, and it had been proved in studies to have benefits for both the physical and mental health of those who participated. This supplement was claimed to lower blood pressure and cholesterol levels, improve cardiovascular health, strengthen weight-bearing bones, aid in the prevention or slowing of bone loss associated with osteoporosis, lessen the risks associated with obesity, and promote greater lung capacity in healthy individuals. The use of dance movement therapy instead of traditional physical exercise for older people may be a feasible alternative since they may reap the most advantages from the benefits that dance movement therapy can bring to anybody at any age, including those who are disabled.

III. Senior Fitness Test Results (With Dance movement therapy Engagement)

**Table 3.1
Chair Stand**

Respondents	Chair stand (no. of stands)
1	10
2	10
3	11
4	11
5	11
6	15
7	10
8	12
9	11
10	12
11	10
12	10
13	11
14	11
15	11
16	15
17	10
18	12
19	11
20	12
21	10
22	10
23	11
24	11
25	11
Weighted Mean	11.16

Table 3.1 represents the senior fitness test results with dance movement therapy engagement. For chair stand, the weighted mean for these 10 respondents who were engaged in dance movement therapy have 11 number of stands which falls into low risk. As noted in Figure 3 and 4 for both men and women.

**Table 3.2
Arm Curl**

Respondents	Arm Curl
1	15
2	10

3	10
4	13
5	13
6	16
7	12
8	13
9	13
10	15
11	15
12	10
13	10
14	13
15	13
16	16
17	12
18	13
19	13
20	15
21	15
22	10
23	10
24	13
25	13
Weighted Mean	12.84

In arm curl, the weighted mean were 13 number of reps. It appears that both senior citizen men and women fell below average as measured in Figure 3 and 4.

Table 3.3
6-Min walk

Respondents	6-Min Walk (no.of yds)
1	240
2	300
3	310
4	230
5	275
6	310
7	220

8	310
9	190
10	325
11	240
12	300
13	310
14	230
15	275
16	310
17	220
18	310
19	190
20	325
21	240
22	300
23	310
24	230
25	275
Weighted Mean	271

For the 6 minutes walk, both men and female senior citizen fell in below average with weighted mean of 271 yards only.

Table 3.4
2-min step

Respondents	2-Min Step
1	58
2	80
3	81
4	63
5	68
6	77
7	65
8	82
9	62
10	63
11	58
12	80

13	81
14	63
15	68
16	77
17	65
18	82
19	62
20	63
21	58
22	80
23	81
24	63
25	68
Weighted Mean	69.92

For 2-min step, both men and female senior citizen fell in below average with weighted mean of 69.9 steps only.

Table 3.5
Back Scratch

Respondents	Back Scratch
1	2 ½
2	3
3	3 ½
4	2
5	2 ½
6	1 ½
7	1 ½
8	1 ½
9	2 ½
10	3
11	2 ½
12	3
13	3 ½
14	2
15	2 ½
16	1 ½
17	1 ½

18	1 ½
19	2 ½
20	3
21	2 ½
22	3
23	3 ½
24	2
25	2 ½
Weighted Mean	2.625

For Back Scratch, both men and female senior citizen fell in below average with weighted mean of 2.2 inches only.

Table 3.6
8-Ft Up-&-Go

Respondents	8-Ft Up-&-Go
1	1
2	3
3	3
4	2
5	2 ½
6	1 ½
7	1 ½
8	1 ½
9	2
10	2 ½
11	1
12	3
13	3
14	2
15	2 ½
16	1 ½
17	1 ½
18	1 ½
19	2
20	2 ½
21	1
22	3

23	3
24	2
25	2 ½
Weighted Mean	2.21

And for 8-Ft Up-&-Go, both men and female senior citizen fell in below average with weighted mean of 5.5 seconds only.

It only noted that senior citizen who were engaged in dance movement therapy have while often rigorous, ballroom dance can be easily tailored to those that require a lower impact physical activity. A variety of dances can be practiced and performed at a slower pace and intensity, more attuned to seniors' needs. Exercise may also be more difficult for you as an older adult, or maybe you're just not getting as much activity into your day as you should. Health problems, arthritis, and soreness may seem like good excuses to skip exercise, but you're doing yourself more harm than good by being sedentary. Research suggests that regular physical activity can help boost memory, improve balance, and prevent depression among people over 65. In order to lessen the possibility of falling and injuring themselves as a result, elderly persons were urged to learn the tango and dance movement therapy. Tango and ballroom dancing, which are slower, more structured dance styles, provide ankle and core strength for senior folks, helping them to keep their balance more effectively in their daily activities. According to research, older people are more likely to fall than younger people because of muscle degeneration and loss of balance that occurs with age, as well as visual problems and prescription side effects. The functional fitness of senior citizens will be explored in this study by the researcher, who will also look at the influence of dance movement therapy on this particular demographic of individuals. The advantages of dance movement therapy, which is a kind of physical exercise, on the functional fitness of older people were investigated since older people had lower levels of physical activity and a more sedentary lifestyle than younger people

IV. Regression Analysis Without Dance Movement Therapy

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.221532642
R Square	0.049076712
Adjusted R Square	0.005852926
Standard Error	1.75131031
Observations	24

<i>ANOVA</i>					
	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	3.482402	3.482402	1.13541	0.29818
Residual	22	67.47593	3.067088		
Total	23	70.95833			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	4.370341615	1.838215	2.377492	0.026548	0.558116	8.182567	0.558116	8.182567
10	0.180124224	0.169042	1.065556	0.29818	-0.17045	0.530697	-0.17045	0.530697

The coefficient of dependent variables (dance movement therapy) has estimated standard error of 1.838215, t-statistic of 2.377492 and p-value of 0.026548. It is therefore concluded that there is significant between the variables at significance level $\alpha = .05$ as $p < 0.05$. The coefficient of independent variables (physical activities) has estimated standard error of 0.169042, t-statistic of 1.065556 and p-value of 0.29818. It is therefore concluded that there is significant between the variables at significance level $\alpha = .05$ as $p < 0.05$.

It shows that dance movement therapy was an important factor in doing physical activities. Dance has been shown to be a culturally adapted physical activity intervention that may promote physical activity while also improving cardiovascular health. Furthermore, dancing may sustain an individual's interest in the activity, implying the possibility of long-term sustainability. Dancing, a collection of dances performed to a range of music, was gaining popularity. The cha-cha, salsa, and rumba are three kinds of dance that are now gaining popularity. Salsa dancers transfer their weight by stepping, which causes the hips, shoulders, and arms to move. The upper body level was maintained while walking and moving the hips, shoulders, and arms. The dancers in rumba move their hips gently. Bending and straightening the knees produced the gradual hip motions.

According to Kattenstroth et al. (2011), senior persons who dance on a regular basis had improved balance, postural stability, flexibility, and physical reaction speed. Alpert et al. (2009) demonstrated gradual balance improvement in the sensory organization test (SOT) in a 15-week study of 13 women aged 52–88 years doing jazz dancing. It also shown that after 24 sessions of low-impact aerobic dancing for 52 individuals aged 68 on average, the dancers improved their dynamic balance but not their static balance in the Time Up-and-Go test.

V. Regression Analysis With Dance Movement Therapy

<i>Regression Statistics</i>	
Multiple R	0.594877
R Square	0.353879
Adjusted R Square	0.32451
Standard Error	1.110081
Observations	24

ANOVA

	<i>df</i>	<i>SS</i>	<i>MS</i>	<i>F</i>	<i>Significance F</i>
Regression	1	14.84816	14.84816	12.04934	0.002169
Residual	22	27.11017	1.23228		
Total	23	41.95833			

	<i>Coefficients</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>	<i>t Stat</i>	<i>P-value</i>	<i>Lower 95%</i>	<i>Upper 95%</i>	<i>Lower 95.0%</i>	<i>Upper 95.0%</i>
Intercept	5.985876	1.521472	3.934266	0.000708	2.830536	9.141216	2.830536	9.141216
15	0.409605	0.118	3.471216	0.002169	0.164887	0.654322	0.164887	0.654322

The coefficient of dependent variables has estimated standard error of 1.521472, t-statistic of 3.934266 and p-value of 0.000708. It is therefore conclude that there is significant between the variables at significance level $\alpha = .05$ as $p < 0.05$. The coefficient of independent variables has estimated standard error of 0.118, t-statistic of 3.471216 and p-value of 0.002169. It is therefore conclude that there is significant between the variables at significance level $\alpha = .05$ as $p < 0.05$.

It shows that dance movement therapy was an important factor in doing physical activities. Senior Citizens were more active than without dance movement therapy. Another research found that regular Physical activities delays the loss of functional skills associated with aging and, in some cases, reverse the loss and morbidity. The activities advised for the elderly should promote or maintain physical and mental health. In senior persons, several types of fitness regimens have been carried out. For many years, any sort of dance was employed as a therapy approach. Dance engages older folks and boosts their motivation. Furthermore, studies have shown that older individuals like engaging in dance programs, which improves their quality of life, balance, and mobility. Dance was defined as an activity that involves several senses, links movement to music, allows for self-expression, and incorporates various parts of personality.

Music, which was a big part of dancing, helps with physical performance. It is simpler to begin moving, walking, dancing, or dealing with any kind of exercise if some individuals listen to their preferred music. During exercise, it reduces weariness and raises levels of psychological stimulation. Furthermore, dancing has been presented as a viable program for the development and improvement of balance as well as the prevention of falls in the elderly. It examined the impact of dance programs on hypertensive individuals with distinct cardiac vascular problems. Hackney and Bennett (2014) tried to assess the influence of Parkinson's disease on dance participation since these patients had mostly mobility issues, with a higher chance of falling and, as a consequence, a worse quality of life. It studied the effect of a Greek dance program on aerobic capacity and muscular tone in 13 persons with hearing difficulties. After 12 weeks of dancing training, substantial improvements in physiological peak metrics such as oxygen consumption and fatigue time were seen. Other studies using Greek traditional dance on women with breast cancer found that it improved their physical functioning, life satisfaction, and reduced depressive symptoms.

VII. Summary and Recommendations

Summary

Seniors who did not participate in dance movement therapy had dangerous health concerns. Seniors who participated in dance movement therapy had no dangerous health issues. The physiologic ability to execute regular daily activities safely and independently without excessive tiredness was defined as dance movement therapy performance.

Dance movement therapy is a terrific kind of exercise for the muscles and the heart, as well as a high cognitive demand. Ballroom dancing has the ability to enhance the cardiovascular outcomes of elderly Filipinos at risk of coronary heart disease. The data may be utilized to further investigate ballroom dancing and other forms of physical activity that helped older citizens.

Recommendations

This study required the commitment and involvement of the concerned personnel to sustain its effectiveness and reliability, thus, the following recommendations were made. Government should implement community-based exercise programs offering a variety of exercise types to people with varying levels of functional ability have both physical and psychosocial benefits for the senior citizen. LGU must have exercise programs in every barangay that teach older adults to move correctly while generalizing movements to activities. Future researcher should be encouraged to pursue other forms of physical activity interventions to improve enjoyment and increase motivation to exercise among senior citizens

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Author Information

Zhao Meng,

School of Music, Shanxi University, Shanxi, China
